

Thiouryl Formazan, Thiazolidinone and Azetidinone Derivatives as Antiparkinsonian Agents

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Substituted thiouryl formazans, thiazolidinones and azetidinones were synthesised and their antiparkinsonian activity was studied. The study showed that thiouryl formazans derivatives having dimethylamino and chloro group, thiouryl thiazolidinones and azetidinones having phenyl, 4-methoxyphenyl group at 2nd and 4th position were found most potent. Some compounds showed lesser toxicity.

FORMAZANS, thiazolidinones and azetidinones from various heterocycles like quinazolinone, piperazine, indole have been found to possess potent antiparkinsonian activity¹⁻³. Thiosemicarbazide, a thiouryl amine, having sulphur atom instead of oxygen, has not been utilised for the synthesis of formazans. The present work describes synthesis and antiparkinsonian activity of thiouryl formazans, thiazolidinones and azetidinones.

Thiourylamine was condensed with aryl aldehydes to yield arylthiosemicarbazones. The latter on reaction with aryl diazonium chlorides, thioglycolic acid and chloroacetyl chloride yielded

1,3-substituted-diphenyl-5-formazan carbothiamides, 4-oxo-2-substituted-phenyl-1-thiazolidinylthioureas and 3-chloro-2-oxo-4-substituted-phenyl-1-azetidinylthioureas respectively (Scheme 1). The structures were confirmed by nmr and mass spectral studies and the compounds were evaluated for their antiparkinsonian activity.

Experimental

The melting points of the compounds were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-

Elmer 137 spectrophotometer, mass spectra on a JMSD 300 instrument fitted with JMA data system at 70 eV and pmr spectra on a Varian A 60D spectrometer.

1,3-Substituted-diphenyl-5-formazan carbothiamide (2): The appropriate amine (0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and hydrochloric acid (1.5 ml) was diazotised with sodium nitrite (0.2 g) in water (2 ml) at 0–5°. This solution was added with stirring to 1-substituted-benzylidene thiourea (1;

0.01 mol in pyridine) in cold and left overnight at ambient temperature. It was then poured into cold water (250 ml) with stirring when a coloured solid separated out, which was filtered, washed repeatedly with water and recrystallised from methanol to give 2 (Table 1): **2a** (Found: C, 52.8; H, 3.0; N, 22.1. $C_{14}H_{12}N_6S$ requires: C, 52.9; H, 3.0; N, 22.0%); ν_{max} 1520 (N=N), 1610 (C=N) and 1070 cm^{-1} (C=S); M^+ at m/z 317/319 (3:1), fragments at m/z 301, 257, 228, 178, 139, 111, 103 and 77 (base peak) (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANTIPARKINSONIAN ACTIVITY DATA OF 1,3-SUBSTITUTED-DIPHENYL-5-FORMAZAN-CARBOTHIAMIDE (2a–h)

Compd. no.*	R ₁	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Antiparkinsonian activity (Reserpine 5 mg/kg in rats)		
				Rigidity %	Hypokinesia % counts	Catatonias (mean score)
2a	4-Cl	110	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₆ S	40 ^a	38.5 ^a	2.2 ± 0.2 ^a
2b	2,4-Cl ₂	95	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₆ S	50 ^a	36.8 ^a	2.4 ± 0.2
2c	2-NO ₂ , 4-Cl	90	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₆ SO ₂	80	12.4	2.8
2d	2-Cl	90	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₆ S	40 ^a	40.2 ^a	2.1 ± 0.1 ^a
2e	4-Cl	125	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₆ S	80	14.3	2.8
2f	2-NO ₂ , 4-Cl	105	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₆ SO ₂	70	9.7	3.0
2g	2,4-Cl ₂	90	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₆ S	60	19.7	2.8
2h	4-OCH ₃	110	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₆ SO	50 ^a	29.5	2.6 ± 0.1
Control	—	—	—	100	6.6	3.0
1-dopa	—	—	—	80	26.5	2.8

*R=H for 2a–c; 4-N(CH₃)₂ for 2d–h; 2a δ (CDCl₃) 8.1–8.5 (2H, bs, 1° thioamidic NH₂), 6.6–6.8 (1H, bs, 2° thioamidic NH) and 7–8.5 (3H, m, ArH).

^aP < 0.05 active compound.

2-(Substituted-phenyl)-4-thiazolidinone-3-ylthioureas (3): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) in DMF (30 ml) and thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) containing a pinch of $ZnCl_2$ (anhydrous) was refluxed for 8 h, then cooled and poured into cold water. A resulting solid was washed and recrystallised to give 3 (Table 2): 3a (Found: C, 47.3; H, 4.3; N, 14.2. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2S_2O$ requires: C, 47.4; H, 4.4; N, 14.2%); ν_{max} 2 850 (CH_2), 1 680 (C=O) and 1 070 cm^{-1} (C=S).

3-Chloro-2-oxo-4-(substituted-phenyl)azetidine-1-ylthioureas (4): To the appropriate 1 (0.01 mol) in dioxane (50 ml) were added chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.01 mol) at 0–5°. It was left at room temperature for 3 h and refluxed for 8 h. The insoluble triethyl amine hydrochloride was then filtered off, the excess solvent distilled off and the reaction mixture was poured into cold water. The resulting solid was washed and crystallised to give 4 (Table 3): 4a (Found: C, 46.9; H, 3.9; N, 16.8. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2SOCl$ requires: C, 47.0; H, 3.9; N, 16.9%); ν_{max} 1 700 (C=O), 1 070 (C=S) and 760 cm^{-1} (C=Cl); M^+ at m/z 255, isotopic peak at m/z 257 (3:1), fragments at m/z 220, 210 (base peak) 207, 179, 178, 104, 102, 90, 89, 77 and 74 (Scheme 3).

Antiparkinsonian activity:

Reserpine induced rigidity, hypokinesia and catatonia in rats: Reserpine (5 mg/kg i.p.) produced

rigidity, hypokinesia (decreased locomotor activity) and catatonia in adult rats weighing 100–120 g. The test compounds were administered in a dose of 100 mg/kg i.p. as aqueous suspension in gum accacia 15 min after reserpine injection. Rigidity was measured 1 h after reserpine and the degree of resistance was scored according to the method of Goldstein *et al.*⁴. Hypokinesia was measured 2 h after reserpine according to the method of Dews⁵. Catatonia was measured 4 h after reserpine injection and scored according to the method of Morpurgo⁶.

The results were statistically analysed. The significance of difference of mean score from control was determined by applying Mann-Whitney U-test⁷.

Acute toxicity study: The compounds which showed significant antiparkinsonian activity were investigated for their acute toxicity (approx. LD_{50}) in mice (20–25 g) of either sex. The compounds were given orally at graded doses to separate group of animals. After 24 h of administration, percent mortality in each group was observed from the data obtained. ALD_{50} value was calculated by the method of Smith⁸.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds exhibited antiparkinsonian activity. 1,3-Substituted-diphenyl-5-formazan car-

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND ANTIPARKINSONIAN ACTIVITY DATA OF 4-OXO-2-SUBSTITUTED-PHENYL-1-THIAZOLIDENYLTHIOUREA (3a–c)*

Compd. no**	R	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Antiparkinsonian activity (Reserpine 5 mg/kg in rats)		
				Rigidity %	Hypokinesia % counts	Catatonia (mean score)
3a	H	150	$C_{10}H_{11}N_2S_2O$	40*	15.5	2.4 ± 0
3b	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	110	$C_{12}H_{13}N_2S_2O$	100	19.1	2.8 ± 0.1
3c	4-OCH ₃	300	$C_{11}H_{12}N_2S_2O_2$	60	28.1	2.6 ± 0.2
Control	—	—	—	100	6.9	3.0
1-dopa	—	—	—	80	26.5	2.8

*Yield = 70–75%; Solvent of crystallisation = DMF/water.

**3a δ (DMF) 8.1–8.5 (2H, bs, 1° thioamidic NH₂), 7–8 (5H, s, ArH), 6.65–6.86 (1H, bs, 2° thioamidic NH), 2.6 (2H, s, CH₂).

*P < 0.05 active compound.

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL AND ANTIPARKINSONIAN ACTIVITY DATA OF 3-CHLORO-2-OXO-4-(SUBSTITUTEDPHENYL)-1-(AZETIDINYL)THIOUREA (4a–c)*

Compd. no**	R	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Antiparkinsonian activity (Reserpine 5 mg/kg in rats)		
				Rigidity %	Hypokinesia % counts	Catatonia (mean score)
4a	H	100	$C_{10}H_{10}N_2SOCl$	80	14.3	2.6 ± 0.1
4b	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	180	$C_{12}H_{12}N_2SOCl$	80	20.5	3.0 ± 0
4c	4-OCH ₃	165	$C_{11}H_{12}N_2SO_2Cl$	60	12.5	2.4 ± 0.2
Control	—	—	—	100	6.6	3.0
1-dopa	—	—	—	80	26.5	2.8

*Yield = 70–75%, Solvent of crystallisation = Dioxane/water.

**4a δ (CDCl₃) 8.1–8.5 (2H, 1° thioamidic NH₂), 7–8 (5H, s, ArH), 6.65–6.85 (1H, bs, 2° thioamidic NH), 1 (1H, s, OH azetididine ring), 1.25 (1H, s, CHCl of azetididine ring).

bothiamides (2a-h) showed antirigidity activity better than 1-dopa. Compounds 2a, 2b, 2d and 2e exhibited better activity than 1-dopa. Compounds 2a, 2b and 2d were significantly antihypokinetic in activity whereas 2a and 2d were potent against catatonia. Compound 2d, containing dimethyl-amino and chloro substituents, was active against all the three parameters tested. Out of the compounds, 2-substituted-phenyl-4-thiazolidenone-3-ylthioureas (3a-c), 3a exhibited significant antirigidity activity and better anticatatonic activity than that of 1-dopa. Compound 3c also showed better activities than that of 1-dopa.

Among 3-chloro-2-oxo-4-(substituted phenyl)-1-azetidinethylthioureas (4a-c), 4a and 4b exhibited antirigidity activity similar to 1-dopa but 4c was better than 1-dopa. None was antihypokinetic like 1-dopa but 4a and 4c showed anticatatonia better than 1-dopa. The ALD₅₀ value of the active compounds 2a, 2b, 2d, 2h, 3a, 3c and 4c was found to be > 1500 mg/kg.

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